

Diffusion and Chemical Reaction in a Plane Sheet

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A problem of simultaneous diffusion and chemical reaction in a plane sheet has been worked out by a powerful operational method due to Heaviside¹. Expressions for C (concentration) and Mt (amount of solute in the sheet) are obtained in a very simple way and some important conclusions are drawn from the concentration distributions and sorption curves. The problem is discussed in two different cases, viz. (I) Surface concentrations are constant, and (II) Surface concentrations vary linearly with time.

The process of simultaneous diffusion and chemical reaction is very important in connection with the reactions in high polymer substances². In addition to this, diffusion may take place within the pores of a solid which can absorb some of the diffusing substance. Examples involving diffusion into living cells and micro-organisms can be cited from biology and biochemistry.

Considerable amount of studies³⁻⁶ have been made on simultaneous diffusion and chemical reaction. Crank⁷ has also considered various cases of diffusion in a plane sheet in absence of chemical reaction. The problem of simultaneous diffusion and chemical reaction in a plane sheet with a view to considering the effects of chemical reaction on the diffusion has, therefore, been discussed in the present paper. The conclusions which are obtained from this present theoretical paper are in agreement with the experimental works of Frank-Kamenetskii⁸.

Solution of the problem :

Let us consider a plane sheet of thickness $2l$, which occupies the region $-l \leq x \leq l$, so that there is symmetry about $x=0$. The equation for our problem is

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D_d \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} - Kc, \quad t > 0, \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where C = concentration at a distance x .

D_d = Diffusion co-efficient.

K = Constant for first order reaction.

The solution of equation (1) is

$$C = A \cos h \left(\frac{D+K}{D_d} \right)^{1/2} x + B \sin h \left(\frac{D+K}{D_d} \right)^{1/2} x, \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where A and B are two unknown constants to be determined from initial conditions and $\frac{d}{dt} = D$ (Operator).

To solve the problem following assumptions have been made :

(1) It has been assumed that all variable quantities depend on only one co-ordinate x , which is perpendicular to the surface. Thus the material transport in the direction parallel to the surface has been neglected. This assumption of one dimensional diffusion is justified in the case of a thin plane sheet, since effectively all the diffusing substances enter through the plane faces and negligible amount through the edges.

(2) Diffusion co-efficient has been assumed to be constant and independent of the concentration. This will apply in practice to diffusion in dilute solutions.

(3) The associated reaction may be of instantaneous type, non-linear type or irreversible type of any order. Among these several kinds of reaction a simple case has been considered, where the diffusing substance is immobilized by an irreversible first order reaction⁷.

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Case I: Surface concentrations are constant i. e.

$$C = C_0, x = l, t > 0 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$C = C_0, x = -l, t > 0, \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Evaluating the arbitrary constants from equations (3) and (4), equation (2) turns out to be

$$C = \frac{C_0}{\text{Cos h} \left\{ \left(\frac{D+K}{D_a} \right)^{1/2} l \right\}} \cdot \text{Cos h} \left\{ \left(\frac{D+K}{D_a} \right)^{1/2} x \right\}. \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Expanding the hyperbolic cosines and simplifying,

$$C = C_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left[\exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{D+K}{D_a} \right)^{1/2} \left((2n+1)l - x \right) \right\} + \exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{D+K}{D_a} \right)^{1/2} \left((2n+1)l + x \right) \right\} \right] \dots \quad (6)$$

Assuming that K is small and expanding the exponential functions, the operational solution of the equation (6) will be

$$\begin{aligned} C = C_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n & \left[\text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} - \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} - \frac{Kt^{1/2}}{D_a^{1/2}} \left\{ \left((2n+1)l-x \right) \text{ierfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right. \right. \\ & + \left. \left. \left((2n+1)l+x \right) \text{ierfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} + \frac{K^2 t}{D_a} \left\{ \left((2n+1)l-x \right) i^2 \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \left((2n+1)l+x \right) i^2 \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} - \right] \dots \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

which reduces to the well-known solution for diffusion without reaction when $K=0$ (Crank⁷).

Total amount M_t of diffusing substance in the sheet as a function of time t is given by

$$M_t = \int_{-l}^{+l} c dx, \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$$\text{or, } M_t = \frac{2C_0}{\left\{ \frac{D+K}{D_a} \right\}} \cdot \tan h \left(\frac{D+K}{D_a} \right)^{1/2} l \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

Expanding the hyperbolic function and assuming that K is small, the operational solution of the equation (9), is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{M_t}{4lC_0} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n & \left[\frac{(D_a t)^{1/2}}{l} \cdot \left\{ \text{ierfc} \frac{nl}{(D_a t)^{1/2}} - \text{ierfc} \frac{(n+1)l}{(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} - 2Kt \left\{ \left\{ n i^2 \text{erfc} \frac{nl}{(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right. \right. \right. \\ & - \left. \left. (n+1) i^2 \text{erfc} \frac{(n+1)l}{(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} + \frac{(D_a t)^{1/2}}{l} \left\{ i^3 \text{erfc} \frac{nl}{(D_a t)^{1/2}} - i^3 \text{erfc} \frac{(n+1)l}{(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} + \frac{2l K^2 t^{3/2}}{(D_a)^{1/2}} \right. \\ & \left. \left\{ n^2 i^3 \text{erfc} \frac{nl}{(D_a t)^{1/2}} - (n+1)^2 i^3 \text{erfc} \frac{(n+1)l}{(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} - \right] \dots \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

Case II: Surface concentrations vary linearly with time i. e.

$$C = \alpha t, x = l, t > 0, \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

$$C = \alpha t, x = -l, t > 0. \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

The solution of the equation (2) subject to the boundary condition (11) and (12) is obtained by the same procedure of case I and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} C = \alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n & \left[(4t) \left\{ i^2 \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} + i^2 \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} - \frac{4Kt^{3/2}}{D_a^{1/2}} \left\{ \left((2n+1)l-x \right) \right. \right. \\ & i^3 \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} + \left. \left. \left((2n+1)l+x \right) i^3 \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} + \frac{4K^2 t^2}{D_a} \right. \\ & \left. \left\{ \left((2n+1)l+x \right)^2 i^4 \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} + \left((2n+1)l-x \right)^2 i^4 \text{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_a t)^{1/2}} \right\} - \right] \dots \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

This equation reduces to the solution for diffusion without reaction when $K=0$.

In this case the total amount of solute M_t in the sheet at time t is obtained by the procedure as used in case of I and is given by

$$\frac{M_t}{16\sqrt{lt}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left[\frac{(D_d t)^{1/2}}{l} \left\{ i^3 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{nl}{(D_d t)^{1/2}} - i^3 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(n+1)l}{(D_d t)^{1/2}} \right\} - 2Kt \left(ni^4 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{nl}{(D_d t)^{1/2}} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - (n+1)i^4 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(n+1)l}{(D_d t)^{1/2}} + \frac{(D_d t)^{1/2}}{l} \left\{ i^3 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{nl}{(D_d t)^{1/2}} - i^3 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(n+1)l}{(D_d t)^{1/2}} \right\} \right) - \frac{K^2 t^2 l}{2(D_d t)^{1/2}} \left(n^2 i^5 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{nl}{(D_d t)^{1/2}} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - (n+1)^2 i^5 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(n+1)l}{(D_d t)^{1/2}} \right) \right] \dots \dots \dots \quad (14)$$

Equations (7), (10), (13) and (14) are computed by taking $Kt=1$. Values of C/C_0 and $C/4\sqrt{ct}$ are calculated for different values of x/l and the values of $M_t/4lC_0$ and $M_t/(16\sqrt{lt})$ are calculated for different values of $I (= D_d t)^{1/2}/l$. It is obvious that the series represented by the equations (7), (10), (13) and (14) are highly convergent and during computation it is observed that for each case the value of the term containing K^2 is very small in comparison with the value of the corresponding term containing K .

Graphical representations of the equations (7), (10), (13) and (14) are shown in Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

Discussion :

From figures 1 and 3 it is clear that at a particular value of I the concentration increases with

Fig. 1. Concentration distribution curves are drawn for three values of $I (= (D_d t)^{1/2}/l)$ under two conditions ; (i) in presence of chemical reaction (represented by full curves) and (ii) in absence of chemical reaction (represented by dashed curves).

an increase of the distance, the increase being rapid for large values of x than for small ones. Also at a fixed distance the concentration increases with an increase in the value of I . The deviation of a full curve from the corresponding dashed curve (which represents the effect of chemical reaction on the concentration distribution) is small for points near the surface

Fig. 2. Sorption curves are drawn under two conditions : (i) in presence of chemical reaction (represented by full curves) and (ii) in absence of chemical reaction (represented by a dashed curve.)

(where $x=1$). It becomes maximum at region well within the sheet, the distance of the region depending on the value of I . Nature of the dashed curves and full curves are same. This means that the concentration distributions are not modified in kind but in degree only for the presence of chemical reaction.

From figures 2 & 4 it is clear that the rate of uptake increases as sorption proceeds but later

Fig. 3. Concentration distribution curves are drawn for different values of $I = (D_0at)^{1/2}/l$; under two conditions : (i) in presence of chemical reaction (represented by full curves) and (ii) in absence of chemical reaction (represented by dashed curves).

decreases as the final equilibrium is approached. Curves of this kind are often referred to as sigmoid sorption curves. They may arise in practice because surface equilibrium conditions are not established instantaneously. At constant values of K and t , and for small values of I , the deviation of a full curve from the dashed curve increases as I increases, the deviation being constant for large values of I . In this case also the nature of the dashed curve and full curves are the same, i. e. the presence of chemical reaction in diffusion cannot modify the sorption distribution in kind but in degree only.

All these theoretical discussions are in accordance with the physical concept and are in agreement with the experimental works of D. A. Frank-Kamenetskii⁶.

Fig. 4. Sorption curves are drawn under two conditions : (i) in presence of chemical reaction (represented by full curves) and (ii) in absence of chemical reaction (represented by a dashed curve).

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